

**Impact of the Diverse Models of Flexible Work Arrangements on Employee
Well-Being and Productivity in the Technology Industry**

Submitted by

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Abstract

The adoption of flexible work arrangements (FWAs) has gained considerable momentum in recent decades as organizations strive to address employee-related challenges, particularly in retaining top talent. This trend was further accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, with the technology industry being at the forefront of FWA implementation. Given the fast-paced, ever-evolving nature of the tech industry, organizations must maintain a competitive edge, often placing employees under significant pressure and impacting their work-life balance. This, in turn, can negatively affect employee well-being, productivity, and, ultimately, organizational performance.

The present study aims to explore the impact of various FWAs on employee well-being and productivity within the technology sector. Specifically, the research focuses on identifying the most effective FWAs, examining their influence on employee well-being, and investigating the relationship between FWAs and productivity. A systematic review methodology was employed, analyzing ten journal articles selected based on predetermined criteria.

Findings indicate that remote working and telecommuting are the most commonly adopted and effective FWAs within the technology industry. Moreover, the study reveals a significant positive impact of FWAs on employee well-being and a strong correlation between FWAs and enhanced employee productivity. Based on these findings, it is recommended that organizations not only encourage the use of FWAs but also actively support their employees' well-being. Effective communication and ongoing support are essential for the successful implementation of FWAs, as failure to do so may lead to adverse effects such as social isolation and absenteeism.

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1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

In the last few years, organisations in several industries have been exploring the implementation of flexible work arrangements (FWAs) for their employees. This trend has intensified with the COVID-19 pandemic, and many organisations now see the significance of continuing to provide FWAs to fulfil the expectations of their employees (Wang, et al., 2021). Notably, organisations in the technology industry have taken the lead in implementing more flexible work arrangements since the beginning, recognizing the numerous advantages they offer. Mainly, these arrangements prioritize the demands of their employees, especially in work-life balancing (Ochieng & Kamau, 2021).

According to Ismail and Michael (2023), FWAs today encompass a variety of modes including remote work, compressed work week, job sharing, flexitime, portfolio careers as well as digital nomadic work. These FWAs allow employees with greater autonomy in organizing their work schedules (Jaafar & Rahim, 2022). However, while some studies have shown that FWAs offer numerous benefits that include increasing well-being, job satisfaction, and productivity among employees, others have indicated a detrimental effect on both employee and organisational perspectives (Dunn et al., 2023). As FWAs are widely implemented in organisations in the Technology Industry, it is vital to understand how they effect on well-being and productivity of employees. Thus, this study intends to conduct a systematic review of existing literature to discover the diverse models of FWAs and their impact on employee well-being and productivity within the tech industry.

1.2 Rationale

In the current competitive environment, managers have to utilize an extensive variety of HR strategies to accomplish their organisational objectives. Thus, they are exploring new strategies for attracting and retaining top personnel, as well as managing the emerging issue of conflicts between work and personal lives (Davidescu, et al., 2020). In this rapid pace of innovation and the constantly changing nature of the tech industry, organisations have to work hard towards maintaining a competitive advantage (Ojo, et al., 2022). In light of this, employees have to work

under pressure and face challenges in work-life balance, resulting in negative consequences that ultimately impact how well the organisation performs (Priya, et al., 2020). Hence, it is crucial to comprehending appropriate FWAs in order to avoid these types of negative consequences and guarantee organisational success. Therefore, researchers found it fascinating to investigate the efficacy of FWAs and how they affect individuals and organisations.

Despite the fact that there is a considerable amount of existing literature on FWAs, there are few studies that assess their influence on both employee well-being and productivity. In addition, it has been observed that despite FWAs being widely adopted in the Technology Industry there is a limitation of existing literature pertaining to this industry. Thus, this study intends to provide actionable insights that might inform organisational policies and practices by exploring the diverse models of FWAs and how they have an effect on well-being and productivity of the employees. Furthermore, this investigation bridges the gaps within the current body of literature by particularly focusing on the Technology industry.

1.3 Scope of the study

This study investigates the effect of FWAs on well-being and productivity of employees, particularly within the technology industry. The research did not limit itself to a specific geographical region to thoroughly evaluate the impact of FWAs on employee well-being and productivity. Furthermore, the study focuses on subsectors and a wide variety of organisational contexts across the technology industry. This process involves examining the models of FWAs including remote working, telecommuting, job sharing, digital nomadism and compressed workweeks as well as their impact on employee well-being and productivity. Through the use of these distinct models, the study aimed to evaluate the different impacts on well-being and productivity of the employees in tech industry.

In order to measure well-being, this study employed indicators such as physical and psychological health, job satisfaction, and work-life balance (Mäkikangas, et al., 2016). The study sought to clarify how FWAs impact on well-being by employing these different types of indicators. Furthermore, in order to measure productivity, this study utilized the indicators such as employee efficiency, output quality, time management and creativity (Tapasco, et al., 2021).

By assessing these indicators, the study intends to reveal the intricate association between the FWAs and productivity of employees.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

This study's aim is to systematically evaluate the impact of different models of FWAs on the well-being and productivity of employees within the tech industry. Accordingly, the following are the defined objectives of this study:

- i. To determine effective models of FWAs implemented in the Technology Industry.
- ii. To examine the influence of FWAs on well-being of employees within the Technology Industry.
- iii. To discover the correlation between FWAs and productivity of employees in the Technology Industry.

1.5 Method of Analysis

In light of the limited timeframe and difficulties in collecting primary data this study employed a systematic review as its research approach. Hence, this study relied on secondary data that was collected from the filtered journal articles. Sources such as Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, PubMed, ProQuest and Emerald Insight were employed to obtain high-quality journal articles. In order to find those articles, specific key words were used, such as "flexible work arrangements," "flexi work," "employee well-being," "employee productivity," and "technology industry". This study uses journal articles that were published within the last 10 years (2014–2024) with the aim of enhancing the validity of theories. The author intends to utilise the "Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)" model in selecting the most appropriate journal articles (Saunders, et al., 2019). Following that, the author will assess the literature review using the deductive approach and subsequently construct a conceptual map and identify relevant themes. Nevertheless, this study will be mostly a qualitative study. Therefore, thematic synthesis will be used to analyse the data.

1.6 Theoretical Framework

This section focuses on the theoretical framework that will be used to direct the study on how FWAs impact the well-being and productivity of employees. This study incorporates theories and models, such as management control theory (MCT), social exchange theory (SET), control theory as well as job demand-resources model (JD-R).

MCT was employed to determine the influence of FWAs on well-being and the productivity of employees as a management tool. According to Sljivic et al. (2015), MCT analyses the dynamics that exist between the management and the staff members within the organisation. Additionally, the researchers argue that strategy facilitates the cultivation of positive interaction inside the organisation which will enhance productivity and the sustainability. The SET serves as a theory that examines how two parties behave in social interactions by weighing the potential advantages and disadvantages through a cost-benefit analysis (Blau, 1964, as cited in Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018). The study of Cheng et al. (2023) proposed that SET can be used to assess the impact of organisations offering FWAs on attitudes and behaviours of employees including, commitment, job satisfaction, and performance.

According to the JD-R model, all job features are divided into two separate types, namely job resources and job demands (Shamsi, et al., 2021). They further argued that Job demands contain the social, organisational and physical components necessitate constant mental and physical effort. However, job resources include a variety of components, including physical, psychological, social, and organizational elements that support employees in achieving their work objectives, reducing work stress, or fostering personal advancement and progress. Putnam et al. (2014) propose that the JD-R model describes overall conditions of working, including both job demands and job resources, which align with the advantages and challenges of FWAs. Accordingly, the findings enable to bring together both the positive and negative effects of FWAs into a single framework when examining their impact on employee well-being (Hoeven & Zoonen, 2015).

1.7 Evidence

Although FWAs have gained popularity in recent years, there is considerable empirical evidence proving the impact of FWAs on the well-being and productivity of employees. Further, few

exceptional studies have been carried out with regard to the technology industry. The findings of the study conducted by Hoeven & Zoonen (2015) supported that FWAs had a substantial influence on the well-being of employees. They have established that FWAs positively affect employee well-being through improved autonomy, work-life balance and communication. Ochieng & Kamau (2021) has discovered a significant correlation between FWAs and the productivity of employees. Their research indicates that employees with more FWAs at the workplace demonstrate an increased level of productivity compared to others. Further, Ojo et al. (2022) carried out an investigation to identify the effect of FWAs on employee performance and productivity within the information and communication technology (ICT) industry. They have tested the impact of telecommuting and job sharing on employee performance and productivity. Their findings reveal that FWAs positively impact employee performance and productivity.

A systematic review has been conducted by Ismail and Michael (2023) to assess how the FWAs affect the productivity and performance of the employees. The study aimed to examine the available literature on the impact of FWAs on employee productivity and performance. Accordingly, the researchers have analyzed 36 journal articles. The findings demonstrate that the effects of FWAs on productivity and performance of employees depends on the specific circumstances. Additionally, it revealed that FWAs could offer both advantageous and disadvantageous consequences. Hackney et al. (2022) have also carried out similar research to examine how FWAs impact productivity and performance. They tested how work-from-home arrangements (WFHA) impact productivity and performance. Accordingly, they analyzed 37 articles related to this phenomenon. The findings revealed that non-mandatory WFHA had a beneficial effect on employee productivity and performance, whereas full-time WFHA had a mixed impact. The findings further suggest that WFHA enhances employee well-being, productivity, and job satisfaction. However, when they engage in work from home for a longer period on a full-time basis, the impact might vary. Accordingly, the aforesaid prior studies provide evidence for the correlation between FWAs and the well-being and productivity of employees, as well as the feasibility of carrying out this study.

2.0 Literature review

This chapter provides a comprehensive review of the current literature, starting with the establishment of a clear understanding of the keywords related to the study. Subsequently, the focus shifts towards theoretical frameworks that will direct the study and explore the effective modes of FWAs adopted in the Technology industry. The primary focus of this review is to analyse the impact of FWAs on both employee well-being and productivity. Furthermore, the final part of the chapter is devoted to identifying the key insights regarding the effects of FWAs on the well-being and productivity of employees through thematic analysis.

2.1 Key Words

Flexible Work Arrangements

It can be identified that the landscape of work has been transformed due to the rapid changes in the labour market conditions and the evolving sociodemographics. Therefore, many organisations have been adopted to FWAs to satisfy the employees needs and achieving the organisation goals. According to Ciarniene & Vienazindiene (2018), FWAs within an organisation are typically classified as formal and informal arrangements. These arrangements offer staff a certain level of autonomy and flexibility in managing and modifying their working time or locations. There are wide range of FWAs including teleworking, remote working, flextime, compressed workweeks, job sharing, gig work and digital nomadism (Paje, et al., 2020).

Employee Productivity

Productivity can be identified as efficient utilization of resources of the organisation in order to generate organisation outputs (Rozlan & Subramaniam, 2020). In other words, it refers to the proportion of the ratio of outputs to inputs within an organisation (Saluy, et al., 2021). Accordingly, employee productivity can be referred to how employees generate output efficiently, utilizing the inputs (e.g., resources, tools, time and skills). As per Selvanathan et al. (2020), when the efforts of employees align with their inputs, organisation will consider these employees possess a higher level of productivity.

Employee Well-being

According to Pagán-Castaño et al. (2020), employee well-being can be defined as ‘a condition of achieving high performance throughout the lifetime encompassing physical, mental and socioemotional functions’. However, the existing body of literature on work-related well-being presents a multifaceted perspective. As per Karapinar et al. (2019), well-being relies on individual experiences and work productivity. The study of Nimmi et al. (2020) has identified the well-being from the perspective of physical and mental health. Furthermore, Boccoli et al. (2022) defined well-being as focusing on the level of interactions and connections among employees or with their supervisor or their organisation.

2.2 Theoretical underpinning

This section describes the theoretical framework that guided this investigation. Accordingly, the job demands-resources model (JD-R), social exchange theory (SET), and management control theory (MCT) were incorporated into this investigation.

Job demands-resources model

The JD-R model is widely recognised as a firmly established theoretical framework within the area of workplace health psychology (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). This model is used to understand the correlation between job characteristics, well-being, and performance among employees. The JD-R model was developed by Bakker and Demerouti in 2007. According to this model, work conditions are able separated into two distinct groups: job demands and job resources (Shamsi, et al., 2021). Job demands include a range of physical, mental, and socio-organisational elements of work that result in a reduction in energy levels and tiredness. These conditions will lead to burnout, stress and poor health (Bilotta, et al., 2021). Job resources encompass a variety of physical, mental, and socio-organisational elements of work that help to achieve job objectives, decrease work pressure, and stimulate individual growth (Adil & Baig, 2018). Accordingly, FWAs such as remote work, flexi time and compressed workweek may impact on job demands and resources. In particular, remote work may reduce job-related stress (job demands) while offering autonomy in managing their work schedules (job resources). Hoeven & Zoonen (2015) identified job autonomy as a significant job resource for FWAs.

Social Exchange Theory

As per Blau (1964, as cited in Tsen et al., 2022), the Social Exchange Theory (SET) suggests that people interact with each other with the aim of maximising benefits and minimising costs. Accordingly, employees assess advantages linked to the autonomy and work-life balance offered through FWAs. Similarly, they are taking into account the possible disadvantages such as the erosion of boundaries between work and personal life (Choi, 2019). Hartner-Tiefenthaler et al. (2023) utilised SET to understand employee perceptions of the FWAs they are offered. They argue that employees felt obligated to “pay back” their organisations for what they benefited from FWAs. Accordingly, the study's findings conclude that there would be a simultaneous improvement in both performance and productivity among the employees.

Management Control Theory

According to Sljivic et al. (2015), MCT plays a pivotal role in identifying the characteristics of relationship between the organisation's management and its employees. Excessive control may hinder the organisational flexibility and capacity for innovation. Thus, it is important to maintain the balance and flexibility through effective management. Managers employ FWAs as a management strategy for attracting and retaining competent workers in order to achieve organisational goals (Egole, et al., 2020). Therefore, MCT serves as an important tool to identify the most effective FWAs and the effects of FWAs on the well-being and productivity of employees. As per Contreras et al. (2020), with the implementation of the FWAs, managers need to adjust to remote leadership and maintain team cohesion and productivity.

2.3 Flexible work arrangements implemented in the Technology Industry

As a result of technological advancement, traditional work structures in the workplace have been redesigned. Modern organisations, especially in the technology industry, embrace new work arrangements. Thus, these organisations have increasingly adopted FWAs as a key approach to responding to the varied requirements of employees and adapting to the ever-changing nature of this industry (Russo, et al., 2024). Accordingly, this section discusses the multifaceted modes of FWAs implemented in technology industry organisations and their characteristics.

Telecommuting, also called telework, became popular as a mode of FWA in the 1990s. Initially, Telecommuting was popular only among ICT-sector organisations. As computers, mobile phones, and the internet became everyday work tools, this became popular in other industries as well (Tavares, 2017). According to Brinzea and Secara (2017), teleworking refers to the practice of carrying out duties remotely using computers, mobile phones, and the internet. However, they may occasionally be required to physically attend to perform their duties at the employer's location. Remote work can be identified as a similar FWA to telecommuting. The main difference among them is that remote workers are not required to physically attend the workplace. Instead, they are allowed to working from their homes, co-working space, or any other remote location (Ferreira, et al., 2021). The research conducted Yang et al. (2022) highlights several organisations in the tech industry, like Facebook, Quora, Twitter, and Square, have started implementing remote work policies that will allow certain staff members to work remotely permanently.

The Compressed Workweek is also regarded as a widely adopted FWA in the Tech industry. Despite the requirement of working five days per week, this mode allows employees to work extended hours each three or four days per week (Munyon, et al., 2023). The typical patterns of this FWA observed are four consecutive days with ten hours each day and three consecutive days with twelve hours each day (Sundo & Fujii, 2005, as indicated in Bhala, 2016). "Job sharing" refers to a voluntary arrangement where two individuals jointly assume the duties, compensation, and benefits of a single full-time job. Further, in this mode, each person works part-time on a regular basis (Thakur, et al., 2018). They emphasize that Job sharing allows for part-time employment while filling full-time positions. This method is separate from other part time employments since necessitating a coordinated approach to workplace obligations. Digital nomadism is a trend among knowledge workers, especially in the tech industry. This FWA is recognised as a form of spatial flexibility and allows professionals to operate remotely from any location worldwide. The nomads are often travelling around the world, staying in affordable places. They only need a laptop, a mobile phone, and a good internet connection to perform their job (McElroy, 2019). In the study by Aroles et al. 2019) highlighted that as this trend gains popularity, it is progressively gaining institutionalisation and professionalisation. As a result, it serves as an expansion of capitalist principles rather than a substitute for them.

2.4 Influence of Flexible work arrangements on employee well-being

The relationship between FWAs and well-being of the employees has garnered some considerable attention within research communities in contemporary times. Accordingly, the focus of this section is to assess the current body of literature, clarify the correlation between FWAs and the employee well-being, as well as ascertain key indicators of this phenomenon. Upon conducting this literature review, it was revealed that FWAs have a multifaceted impact on the well-being of employees. For instance, certain studies have established a positive correlation between these two factors, while some studies have shown an opposite view. Also, some other studies argue that there is no significant correlation between them.

The study conducted by Altındağ and Siller (2014) found a positive correlation between FWAs and the employee satisfaction. It was determined that FWAs allow employees to rest and enhance the motivation, thereby enhancing their well-being. Uglanova and Dettmers (2017) also investigated the impact of Flexitime (employer-oriented and employee oriented) on well-being. They examined three patterns of well-being by utilising data from eleven waves (2003-2013) of the German Socio-Economic Panel. In this study well-being was assessed by examining leisure time and work satisfaction. The findings suggests that “Employer-oriented flexibility” has a detrimental effect on job satisfaction, leisure time and ultimately, well-being of employee. However, they discovered that “employee-oriented flexibility” has a beneficial effect on job satisfaction and consequently, on employees’ well-being.

Henke et al. (2016) observed that the health of staff will improve as a result of the implementation of teleworking. The researchers used employees between the ages of 18 and 64 who were actively employed and had completed the health risk assessment during the period of 2010–2011 as participants. Further, the study revealed that employees who are not allowed to telecommute are at greater risk of poor health. Allen et al. (2015) suggests that the FWAs such as telecommuting have been found to effectively mitigate work, non-work conflicts. Delanoeije and Verbruggen (2020) also carried out a similar research to identify the effect of FWAs on well-being indicators (i.e., stress level, work-life conflict) and employee performance. Their findings

indicated that employees who were allowed to perform telework, experienced less stress and work-life conflicts.

Song and Gao (2020) carried out a study to identify the effect of working from home arrangements on the well-being of staff. Their findings revealed that the stress level of employees who are working from home is higher than that of those who are working at the workplace. Moreover, there is a negative correlation between staff members who work remotely on weekdays and their happiness level. The study further demonstrated that working remotely from home has an influence on individuals' subjective well-being, depending on parental status and gender. The study by Elst et al. (2017) sought to examine the correlation between telecommuting and the staff members' well-being who are in the telecommunication sector. They employed a survey to evaluate psychosocial risk factors and employees' well-being in the workplace. The study included a sample size of 878 employees from an international telecommunication firm. The selected employees had a significant track record of telecommuting. The findings pointed out that there is no clear link between telecommuting and indicators of well-being. However, the findings indicate there is an indirect relationship between telecommuting and well-being, which is mediated by social support. Hence, considering the limited social support available to telecommuters, they determined that telecommuting has a negative effect on employee well-being.

2.5 Correlation between Flexible work arrangements and employees' productivity

The literature mostly concentrated on the influence of FWAs on employees' work-life balance and satisfaction, with comparatively less emphasis on employee productivity. The FWAs offer employees the freedom that they need. Consequently, these employees are more likely to make valuable contributions to the success of the organisation in the most effective way possible (Berkery, et al., 2017). Houghton et al. (2017) discovered a substantial correlation between FWAs and productivity of staff. For this study, they have included a sample size of 47 participants across different institutions in Queensland. It was noted that the participants showed great satisfaction with the FWAs, especially the freedom of an alternative workplace. Preenen et al. (2015) carried out a study to examine the effects of internal workforce flexibility policies on both worker

productivity and innovation performance within organisations. This was examined through separate research utilizing distinct datasets at the organisation level. The results indicated that internal workforce flexibility policies improve worker productivity, creativity and innovation performance within organisations.

In order to identify the relationship between intensity of telework and employee productivity, Hoornweg et al. (2016) carried out a study including 111 teleworkers within the banking sector. They have developed and examined a set of hypotheses using the JD-R model. Accordingly, they found a significant correlation between the intensity of telework and productivity. Furthermore, they determined that the impact of productivity depends on the hours worked in the office and the degree of telework intensity. Findings by Gragnano et al. (2020) showed that employees have more concerns about their health as well as that of their families. Thus, they argued that conflicts in the work-life balance would have an impact on labour productivity. They further emphasized that FWAs support employee work-life balance, leading to enhanced productivity. Chung & Lippe (2020) also observed a positive correlation between FWAs and labour productivity. They argued that FWAs enhance employee efficiency and productivity significantly. Moreover, the study suggested that gender and context have an important role in understanding the outcomes of the FWAs. Davidescu et al. (2020) carried out a study that found similar findings, demonstrating employee productivity and performance were greatly impacted by flexible working hours.

Ross & Ali (2017) came up with several significant findings pertaining to the implementation of FWAs throughout ICT sector companies. Their study primarily focused on the characteristics that influence commitment among ICT professionals. They observed that FWAs significantly increase organisational commitment as well as productivity. Furthermore, Allen et al. (2015) conducted research to ascertain the effects of telecommuting. To enhance their comprehension of telecommuting and its consequences, they reviewed existing studies related to the field. Accordingly, they were able to identify several benefits and drawbacks of telecommuting. They further highlighted telecommuting as an FWA with a beneficial influence on productivity and performance of employees.

Although the aforementioned research demonstrate that FWAs had a favourable influence on labour productivity, there are also studies indicating the opposite. The study by Molino et al. (2020) explored that FWAs, specifically remote working, had a detrimental effect on labour productivity and performance. The researchers conducted two studies. The first study involved 878 participants, and the second study involved 749 participants. These studies revealed that FWAs might lead to increased work stress and work-family conflicts, ultimately resulting in a decrease in productivity and performance. They argue that there are a number of factors that might be related to this, including the amount of work and prolonged hours of work.

In summary, the chapter defined the key words used in this study, together with the theoretical frameworks that were utilised to guide the study. Then, this chapter analyses the existing body of literature regarding the study’s three primary objectives. Finally, the concept map of the current research was developed through the thematic synthesis process, as indicated in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Concept map from thematic synthesis

Source: Author developed

3.0 Analysis

This chapter covers the research design, the process of choosing journal articles and descriptive summary of those chosen journal articles. In addition, this chapter presents a concise summary of the method employed for the data analysis of this study.

3.1 Research Design

Researchers can employ a variety of strategies such as primary surveys, systematic reviews, primary case studies, secondary case studies and archival research (Saunders, et al., 2019). Upon analysing the essence of the current investigation, the author observed that the survey approach based on primary data is more appropriate for this study. However, taking into account the time constraints and, cost it is deemed unfeasible. Furthermore, as per the guidelines provided by the university, the author is only allowed to use secondary data for this study. Thus, considering all of these factors and weighing the advantages and disadvantages, the author decided to employ a systematic review strategy in this study to gather and analyse data. Accordingly, this study utilized peer-reviewed journal articles that were published within the last decade. The correlation between FWAs and labour productivity and well-being in the technology industry has been synthesised using these literatures. Further, this research uses secondary data to evaluate and analyse the association between those three variables using a deductive approach, while validating the predetermined objectives.

3.2 Article selection process

During this step, the author meticulously determined the keywords that are going to be utilized to find the appropriate journal articles that align with the objectives of the study. The specified keywords include "flexible work arrangements," "alternative work schedules," "remote work," "flexi time," "work from home," "teleworking," "telecommuting," "flexible hours," "employee productivity," "employee well-being," "employee performance," and "employee satisfaction." The search of articles was conducted using those pre-defined keywords through journal databases such as Google Scholar, Emerald Insight, PubMed, and ProQuest. The author gathered relevant journal articles from multiple databases to produce a comprehensive research paper

that offers the most practical and applicable solutions. Table 3.1 below indicates the procedure for choosing journal articles.

Criteria	Elements
Journal database	Google Scholar Emerald Insight PubMed ProQuest
Source	Academic Journals Research papers
Search words	“Impact of Flexible arrangements” “Flexible arrangements and employee productivity” “Flexible arrangements and employee well-being” “Flexible arrangements and employee health” “Flexible arrangements adapted within technology industry” “Productivity of employees in technology industry” “Well-being of employees in technology industry” “Remote working and employee satisfaction” “Flexible work schedules and productivity” “Relationship between flexible work arrangements and productivity” “Relationship between flexible work arrangements and well-being”
Search filters	Google Scholar Year sorted by 2014 to 2024 Article Sorted by relevance Type sorted by reviewed articles Selected articles which include citations

	<p>Emerald Insight</p> <p>Type: Journal articles</p> <p>Date range: 2014 to 2024</p> <p>Access type: Only content I have access to</p> <p>PubMed</p> <p>Text availability: Free Full Text</p> <p>Article type: Not selected any</p> <p>Publication date: 10 years</p> <p>Additional filters were not used.</p> <p>ProQuest</p> <p>Limit to: Full Text and Peer reviewed</p> <p>Publication Date: 2014 to 2024</p> <p>Source type: Scholarly Journals</p>
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Table 3.1: The procedure for choosing journal articles Source: Author developed

3.2.1 Inclusion and exclusion process

The author has identified and collected the journal articles for this study as specified in Table 3.1. Those collected articles were published throughout the recent decade. However, the majority of the chosen articles were from the years 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023 chosen for their abundance and relevance of content. The figure 3.1 demonstrates the screening process employed in this study. The screening and selection process can be identified as one distinctive feature of a systematic review, which is known as "inclusion and exclusion" criteria (Bearman, 2012, cited in Chong et al., 2022). For this process “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)” model is commonly utilised in systematic reviews (Saunders, et al., 2019). Accordingly, out of 71 journal articles gathered, the author was able to select the 10 most relevant articles for analysis employing the PRISMA model.

Figure 3.1: PRISMA Model

Source: Author developed

3.3 Descriptive summary

This phase of a systematic review is referred to as the compilation of a descriptive summary. Accordingly, the author has effectively reviewed 10 journal articles. Consequently, the author was able to determine crucial aspects such as the methodologies employed, the sample characteristics, methods of analysis, and key findings. This information will assist with the conduct of the current research. Table 3.2 presents the descriptive summary of the current study.

Author	Topic	Research Methodology/Sample/Method of Analysing/Industry	Key findings
Onyekwelu et al. (2022)	Flexible Work Arrangements and Workplace Productivity: Examining the Nexus	Survey, Quantitative	FWAs exhibit a strong positive impact on employee and workplace productivity.
		234 responders were selected from Small and medium-sized enterprises across 6 states in Nigeria	
		Both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed	
		SMEs in Nigeria	The implementation of FWAs leads to more control over the workplace.
Hashmi et al. (2023)	Impact of flexible work arrangements on employees' perceived productivity, organisational commitment and perceived	Survey, A quantitative and non-experimental correlational design	FWAs had a positive influence on individuals' reported productivity, commitment to the organisation and perceptions of work quality
		592 respondents	Happiness mediates the positive correlation

	work quality: a United Arab Emirates case-study	Purposive sampling - Individuals currently employed in various service industries in UAE (Both public and private sector).	between FWAs and perceived productivity and commitment to the organisation.
		Through an online survey	This arrangement enables employees to balance their private and professional obligations by taking advantage of their preferred work style.
		Both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed	
		Service industries in UAE	
Conradie and Klerk (2019)	To flex or not to flex? Flexible work arrangements amongst software developers in an emerging economy	Survey, Quantitative	FWAs are widely adapted by the software development companies in Africa.
		277 responses The voluntary sampling method was used	
		Data were collected through an anonymous web-based survey	The findings confirm that FWAs provide advantages for both employees and employers.
		Software developing sector in South Africa	
Agbanu et al. (2023)	Flexible Work Arrangements and Productivity of Sales Representatives of Book	A cross-sectional survey was employed. Quantitative	FWAs, such as telecommuting, job sharing, flexi-time and part-time work had a strong positive correlation with
		Convenience sampling technique	

	Publishing Companies in Nigeria	200 responses (Sales representatives amongst the top ten publishers in Nigeria) Responses were analysed using descriptive statistics Publishing industry in Nigeria	individual efficacy and efficiency.
Hyder and Rani (2024)	Work Flexibility and Work-Life Interface: Linking Formal Flexible Arrangements to Employee Job Satisfaction	Survey, Quantitative Cluster sampling technique	Individuals who are granted permission to work under FWAs report a greater degree of satisfaction than others.
		409 respondents (doctors and nurses) within primary health care hospitals in Pakistan	
	Employed descriptive statistics		
	Health care industry in Pakistan		
Chaudhuri et al. (2022)	Work from anywhere and employee psychological well-being: moderating role of HR leadership support	Survey, Quantitative	Work-from-anywhere flexibility (WAF) positively effect on the employees' psychological well-being (PWB) and safety. Those factors significantly boost employee satisfaction, resulting in improved company performance.

		<p>A total of 962 participants from 14 multinational companies across Asia and Europe were targeted. However, only 486 individuals responded within the given time period.</p>	<p>HR leadership support plays a crucial and beneficial mediating role in facilitating the establishment of adaptable HR policies and suitable organisational structures that enable workers to work remotely from any place.</p>
		<p>To analyse the data “The partial least squares structural equation modelling technique” was used.</p>	
Haridas et al. (2021)	Impact of Work from Home Model on the Productivity of Employees in the IT Industry	<p>Survey, Quantitative</p>	<p>Work from home arrangements offer benefits as well as challenges for both employees and organisations.</p>
		<p>115 employees in IT industry participated (age limit 21-50).</p>	
		<p>Descriptive analysis and factorial analysis were used.</p>	
		<p>IT industry</p>	<p>The productivity of remote workers is significantly influenced by effective communication and teamwork.</p>
Shifrin and Michel (2021)	Flexible work arrangements and employee health: A meta-analytic review	<p>Systematic Review</p>	<p>FWAs positively affect the physical health of employees.</p>
		<p>30 Journal articles and 3 dissertations were used.</p>	<p>FWAs correlated with lower absenteeism, and less physical discomforts.</p>

Šiber and Cero (2024)	Impact of Flexible Working Arrangements on Employee Satisfaction within the IT Sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina	Survey, Quantitative	There are several ways in which remote work positively impact on employee satisfaction including increased productivity, work-life balance and private time.
		122 respondents (IT employees) Convenience sampling method was employed.	
		Multiple regression statistical techniques were used to analysed the data.	
		IT Sector, Bosnia and Herzegovina	Both hybrid workplaces and flexi hours positively associated with employee satisfaction.
Rañeses et al. (2022)	Investigating the Impact of Remote Working on Employee Productivity and Work-life Balance: A Study on the Business Consultancy Industry in Dubai, UAE	Survey, Quantitative	Productivity of employees is positively impacted by remote work. They found that the chance of task completion for remote workers has significantly increased.
		96 respondents Employed purposive Sampling method	
		Descriptive statistics technique was employed to analyse the data.	Remote working does not significantly impact employees' work-life balance.
Consultancy Industry, Dubai			

Table 3.2: Descriptive summary

Source: Author developed

3.4 Method of data analysis

This study incorporates several survey data and definitions. Using those secondary data, the author evaluated the effects of FWAs on employees' well-being and productivity within the technology industry. Denscombe (2017) stated that in business research, there are three different approaches, such as qualitative, quantitative, and mixed approaches. Further, Saunders et al. (2019) argue that qualitative and quantitative methodologies are classified based on the numerical and non-numerical data utilised. Accordingly, the author employed thematic synthesis to assess the data from the 10 chosen articles, as described in table 3.2.

In summary, this chapter discussed the research design. This study uses secondary data, specifically journal articles published within the last decade. This study also employed the systematic review method to gather and analyse data. The author employed the PRISMA model to select the 10 most appropriate journal articles for the study. Finally, The study employed the thematic synthesis approach to evaluate those 10 chosen journal articles.

4.0 Discussion

According to Denscombe (2017), this chapter covers three aspects of the study. Firstly, it aims to discuss the primary insights derived from the thematic analysis. Secondly, it seeks to identify apparent patterns and interrelationships among the data. Finally, it attempts to synthesize both to provide a comprehensive explanation of the findings. On the other hand, Saunders et al. (2019) highlight that this chapter of the study provides opportunity for researchers to apply their intuition. They recommended organizing this chapter with regard to the primary focuses of the current study. In this sense, the author aims to successively accomplish key objectives and critically analysing the key insights of both thematic analysis and descriptive summary.

4.1 Exploring the models of Flexible work arrangements implemented in the Technology Industry

As indicated in the literature review, the technology industry is a prominent industry that extensively employs FWAs. According to Russo et al. (2024) tech companies endeavour to implement FWAs in order to accommodate the evolving industry landscape and meet the demands of their workforce. In the evidence, Šiber & Cero (2024) also indicated that due to dynamics of the industry, organisations trying to provide flexible work options for their employees. The authors emphasise that organisations view FWAs as an approach to attract and retain top talent as well as enhance employee satisfaction. Haridas et al. (2021) also added that FWAs have become a more prominent strategy among the tech companies. They observed that FWAs have gained more popularity with the COVID-19 pandemic. Even after the pandemic, they are willing to continue offering more flexible arrangements for their employees, considering the benefits that it brings.

The literature review revealed the existence of five models of FWAs adapted within the technology industry, including teleworking, remote working, job sharing, a compressed workweek, and digital nomadism. According to Tavares (2017), telecommuting, or teleworking, was a widely adopted FWA in the ICT sector in the 1990s. The author pointed out that, it has gained popularity in other industries as well due to advancements in technology. According to the evidence, Conradie and Klerk (2019) discovered through their research that telecommuting

is a widely used flexible arrangement in the tech industry, particularly in the software development sector. However, they noted that those arrangements were more successful in established nations as opposed to emerging nations. Furthermore, they observed that the effectiveness of these arrangements increases when multiple arrangements are applied together, rather than relying on a single one. Remote working is a form of FWA similar to Telecommuting. Yang et al. (2022) found that remote working is a highly preferred form of FWA within the technology industry. They observed that the biggest tech companies in the world offered their employees permanent remote working opportunity. This was proven by Šiber and Cero (2024), who stated that remote working is a commonly implemented FWA in tech industry. They discovered that most IT companies gave priority to providing remote working options for their employees. They used such strategies to ensure the success of their companies. The study by Haridas et al. (2021) also confirmed that remote working is an effective mode of FWA in the IT sector. Their study was focused on the IT sector in India.

The literature review found that the compressed workweek is a widely used form of FWA in the technology industry, as pointed out by Munyon et al. (2023). In the evidence, the findings of Agbanu et al. (2023) claim that the compressed workweek is a widely used model of FWAs. In the evidence, the findings of Agbanu et al. (2023) claim that the compressed workweek is a commonly utilized form of FWAs. They further recommended that future researchers who examine FWAs to focus on this model, as it is crucial. Furthermore, Hashimi et al. (2023) indicated that a compressed workweek is a popular form of FWA. Their findings demonstrates that the compressed workweek is an effective FWA. However, the research carried out by Agbanu et al. (2023) and Hashimi et al. (2023) do not primarily focus on the technology industry. As a result, the available evidence is insufficient to prove that a compressed workweek is an effective FWA adapted in the technology industry. According to the literature, job sharing also widely recognized as a popular form of FWAs in the technology industry. Nevertheless, there is insufficient evidence to substantiate this claim. Furthermore, the literature review identifies digital nomadism as a developing trend in the technology industry (Aroles, et al., 2019). Nevertheless, this statement also could not be verified due to insufficient evidence.

4.2 Impact of Flexible work arrangements on well-being of employees within the Technology Industry

As per the literature review, it is evident that researchers have given considerable attention to the effects of FWAs on employees' well-being. Accordingly, the findings of Altındağ and Siller (2014) revealed that FWAs enable employees to get sufficient rest and enhance their motivation. These factors will increase employee satisfaction, ultimately leading to their well-being. The study by Uglanova and Dettmers (2017) examined the effects of FWAs, particularly flexitime, on well-being of staff. They found that employer-oriented schedules exhibited a detrimental effect on employee well-being, while employee-oriented schedules had a positive impact. In the evidence, the findings of the study conducted by Hyder and Rani (2024) determined that workers who were given the opportunity to use FWAs reported increased job satisfaction, which led to improved well-being. They discovered that FWAs have a favourable impact on certain aspects of job satisfaction, such as perceived autonomy, work-life balance, and the significance of the tasks they perform. The study specifically focused on flexi-time and part-time work arrangements. The authors argue that organisations can effectively attract and retain talent by implementing formal FWAs as strategic tools. However, the authors suggest that FWAs may also have negative consequences. They emphasise the significance of upholding a good work-life balance while effectively setting boundaries in order to reap the advantages of such arrangements.

As mentioned in the literature, Henke et al. (2016) observed that the adaptation of FWAs, particularly teleworking, increased the health condition of the staff members. Further, their findings claim that employees who are not allowed flexible work arrangements are prone to poor health conditions. According to evidence, Shifrin and Michel (2021) determined that FWAs had a favourable effect on well-being of staff and their physical health. In addition, they found that FWAs will decrease physical discomfort and the level of absenteeism. However, the findings suggest that if the work environment does not provide support, those flexible arrangements will not be effective. For instance, if the employees are not getting support from their superiors, peers, or organisation, they will have adverse career consequences. In addition, employees may exhibit antagonistic behaviours or attitudes, leading them to believe that providing such flexibility is inappropriate. Such factors may hinder the productivity of both personnel and the

company as a whole. Thus, they recommended that company should offer ongoing assistance to their employees and maintain effective communication, which is also vital.

Allen et al. (2015) revealed that FWAs can effectively assist in mitigating the work and non-work conflicts. Further, a similar investigation carried out by Delanoetje and Verbruggen (2020) revealed that FWAs improve employee performance and well-being indicators, which include work-life conflicts and stress levels. The researchers conducted separate investigations of employees who were granted work flexibility and those who were not. It was determined that employees who were offered flexibility in work exhibited greater levels of work engagement and performance. In addition, they observed lower levels of stress and work-life conflicts compared to those who were not offered flexibility in work. In the evidence, it was identified that two studies supported the aforementioned arguments. Hyder and Rani (2024) found that FWAs support employees to minimise their stress level, manage their work schedules, and gain better control over their non-public responsibilities. Their conclusions also indicate a positive relationship between FWAs and various aspects of job satisfaction, particularly work-life balance. Further, findings revealed that the strategic use of FWAs can effectively mitigate both work and non-work conflicts. The authors emphasise that to mitigate adverse outcomes such as burnout and boredom, management needs to cultivate an atmosphere of support and allocate the required resources to assist staff in overcoming such issues. The research carried out by Chaudhuri et al. (2022) also indicated that FWAs positively impact psychological health of employees. According to the findings, firms can effectively assist their staff members to reduce stress and conflicts between work and personal life by successfully implementing FWAs. They highlight that these factors will lead to enhanced employee satisfaction and well-being ultimately enhancing overall performance of the organisation.

In the literature, the findings of Song and Gao (2020) suggest that there is a negative correlation between FWAs and employee well-being. It was shown that the employees who are offered FWAs report higher levels of stress than other employees. In the evidence, the study by Chaudhuri et al. (2022) demonstrates that FWAs improve the well-being of staff members. Song and Gao (2020) conducted their study using the information obtained from the "American Time Use Survey Well-Being Modules" collected in 2010, 2012, and 2013. Therefore, none of the

studies included in the descriptive summary support this finding. Further, Elst et al. (2017) concluded that there is no significant direct correlation between FWAs and well-being factors, particularly work-life balance. Nevertheless, they observed that there exists an indirect relationship between FWAs and well-being which is mediated by social support. Additionally, it was discovered that FWAs have no substantial effect on psychosocial risk factors in the workplace. In the evidence, Shifrin and Michel (2021) found that FWAs assist in increasing the well-being of staff members. They have also emphasised the crucial role of social support in the execution of FWAs to positively affect employee well-being. Rañeses et al. (2022) found that FWAs have no substantial impact on work-life balance. However, their study solely focused on the consulting industry in Dubai. Further, they particularly analysed a sample of 96 remote employees who were employed in administrative and office roles within multiple companies in Dubai. Furthermore, it was noted that out of ten evidences, only one supports the claim. Thus, it is difficult to prove that FWAs do not significantly affect work-life balance.

4.3 Correlation between Flexible work arrangements and productivity of employees in the Technology Industry

In the literature review, Berkery et al. (2017) suggest that by providing FWAs, employees will get the freedom they need, which will enhance their efficiency and ultimately lead to the success of the organisation. Further, a study by Houghton et al. (2017) demonstrates similar insights. They found that the participants in the study showed great satisfaction with the freedom they had with the FWAs. As a result, employees perceive increased productivity. Their findings align with the findings of Hashimi et al. (2023) which reveal that the staff members who are granted FWAs reported satisfaction with the freedom they gain. They further found that through the flexibility, the level of employee commitment had increased. They suggested that it can lead to a reduction in work-life conflicts, eventually resulting in an enhancement in productivity. Moreover, they observed that, through the implementation of the FWAs, employee absenteeism also decreased. Preenen et al. (2015) revealed that implementing flexible working strategies enhances labour productivity. Furthermore, the study determined that these strategies positively affect the creativity and innovation performance of the organisation. This finding is consistent with the

outcomes of the investigation conducted by Onyekwelu et al. (2022). Their findings indicated that implementing FWAs can enhance both employee and organisational productivity. They further claim that FWAs will enhance employee commitment and engagement as well as the innovation performance of organisations. Furthermore, they discovered that these factors had positive effects on employees' work-life balance. However, there is no clear evidence to support the notion that FWAs positively impact on creativity of the employees. Thus it is difficult to validate that finding.

As per the literature review, a study by Hoornweg et al. (2016) found a strong association between the the intensity of telecommuting and productivity. Further, they discovered that the impact of productivity contingent upon both the time dedicated to office work and the level of telecommuting intensity. In the evidence, In the evidence, Haridas et al. (2021) explored the substantial impact of telecommuting on productivity. However, they found that collaboration and interaction exert the greatest influence on the productivity of telecommuters. There is insufficient data to substantiate the claim that the productivity of telecommuters depends on the time they spend at work and the level of telecommuting intensity. Furthermore, in the literature, findings of Gragnano et al. (2020) demonstrates that employee are deeply concerned about their health and their families. Consequently, work-life conflicts will adversely affect the productivity of the employees. Accordingly, the findings suggests that FWAs facilitate employees in achieving work-life balance which will increase productivity. The findings of Onyekwelu et al. (2022), Hashimi et al. (2023), and Agbanu et al. (2023) support the above-mentioned findings. Accordingly, Onyekwelu et al. (2022) state that FWAs facilitate employees in attaining an enhanced work-life balance which improves both employee and organisational productivity. Further, the research conducted by Hashimi et al. (2023) and Agbanu et al. (2023) indicate that implementing FWAs leads to higher employee satisfaction and achieves more work-life balance, resulting in increased productivity.

According to the literature review, the studies of Chung & Lippe (2020) and Davidescu et al. (2020) have shown that FWAs enhance employee productivity significantly. In the evidence, the findings of Rañeses et al. (2022) validate the aforementioned conclusions. They concluded that FWAs, particularly remote working, showed a notable and positive correlation with workers'

productivity. Additionally, a study conducted by Hashimi et al. (2023) observed that FWAs are strongly and positively correlated with individuals' perceived productivity. In the literature review, Ross & Ali (2017) observed that through the implementation of FWAs, employee commitment and productivity will increase. The outcomes of the above investigation are in line with the outcomes of Hashimi et al. (2023). They also concluded that employees who were granted FWAs exhibited a greater degree of productivity and commitment towards the organisation. Furthermore, in the literature review, Allen et al. (2015) discovered that telecommuting significantly improves the productivity of employees. The findings are consistent with the research by Rañeses et al. (2022) and Haridas et al. (2021) that found telecommuting significantly increases the productivity of staff.

However, in the literature review, Molino et al. (2020) revealed that FWAs have a detrimental impact on employee productivity. They have conducted two studies to assess the impact of remote work in the Italian setting amid the COVID-19 pandemic. The both surveys included public and private sector employees who were provided FWAs. They revealed that remote working positively impacts technostressors, resulting in work-life conflicts. Consequently, they discovered a decline in productivity of employees. However, it is noted that these two studies are not directly relevant to the specific industry being examined in the current study. Furthermore, these studies were carried out throughout the COVID-19 pandemic where remote working were mandatory. Rañeses et al. (2022) demonstrated that remote work arrangements brought some challenges for employees who had to adjust to FWAs during the pandemic. However, the study revealed that FWAs exhibit a solid and favourable correlation with the productivity of the staff. Thus, it is difficult to validate the findings of Molino et al. (2020), as most of the conclusions in the evidence demonstrate that FWAs strongly and positively affect the productivity of employees.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The focus of this systematic review was to explore the effects of diverse models of FWAs on the well-being and productivity of employees within the technology industry. The first chapter of this report consists of the background of the study, rationale, scope, aims and objectives, method of analysis, theoretical background, and evidence. In this chapter, the author establishes three objectives to achieve the primary aim of the study. Accordingly, the first objective was to ascertain the most effectively adapted FWAs in the tech industry. The second objective was to investigate how FWAs affect the well-being of workers. The third objective was to examine the correlation between FWAs and the employee productivity. The primary sources for this descriptive study were journal articles published between 2014 and 2024. In order to obtain quality articles the author utilised journal databases including, Google Scholar, Emerald Insight, PubMed, and ProQuest. Further, this chapter illustrated the theories theoretical framework that guided the present study including JD-R model, SET and MCT.

The second chapter includes the definitions of the key words, pre-defined studies and theoretical frameworks that are pertinent to the area of the present study. The chapter begins by providing concise definitions of key words used in this study. The theoretical underpinning extensively discussed the theories, frameworks and models employed in the study with the support of previous studies. Following that, the primary three objectives were thoroughly discussed with the support of relevant literature. According to the literature, the author discovered the most effective FWAs arrangements adapted within the Tech industry. These consist of remote working, telcommuting, job sharing, compressed workweek and digital nomadism. The author then explored how FWAs impact employees' well-being. Consequently, it was discovered that FWAs exhibit a significant favourable effect on employees' well-being. In addition, a single study concluded that social support play as a mediator between FWAs and well-being. However, a few studies have concluded that FWAs exhibit an adverse effect on the employees' well-being. Later on, the author discussed about the relationship between FWAs and the productivity of the employees. Most studies have demonstrated a strong positive correlation between the FWAs and the productivity of employees. Only one study demonstrates a negative correlation between FWAs and employee productivity.

Chapter three consists of Analysis, and it primarily focuses on the relevant implications and conclusions. In the descriptive summary table, this information was properly listed. The PRISMA model represent the procedure of choosing articles based on the research topic. The fourth chapter contains the findings and discussion of the current research. The discussion was done separately according to the key objectives of this investigation. The findings revealed that Remote working and Teleworking/Telecommuting are the most effective and widely adapted modes of FWAs within the technology industry. The findings does not substantiate the other modes including job sharing, compressed workweeks and digital nomadism.

The current findings indicate that through the FWAs, employees are getting the rest they want, which will enhance their motivation and job satisfaction. These factors will increase the well-being of the employees. Further, it has been discovered that organisations utilise FWAs as a strategy to enhance job satisfaction and attract and retain top individuals. Moreover, the study indicated that FWAs positively impact the mental and physical well-being of the staff. However, it was recognised in order to get the maximum impact of FWAs support from the organisation, the involment of both superiors and peers are vital. Accordingly, the study's findings highlight that FWAs enhance the well-being of staff members.

The findings indicate that by implementing FWAs, organisations can obtain higher employee satisfaction and commitment, resulting in enhanced productivity. Furthermore, the findings suggest that FWAs will increase the organisation's innovation performance. Moreover, it has been discovered that by successfully implementing FWAs, organisations can reduce employee absenteeism. Finally, findings demonstrate that collaboration and interaction exert the most significant impact on the productivity of telecommuters. In conclusion, these findings underscore the presence of a strong positive correlation between the FWAs and the productivity of the employee.

The FWAs are gaining popularity in today's organizations because they offer efficient responses to a wide range of contemporary concerns. The findings confirm that FWAs significantly and favourably affect both the well-being and productivity of individuals within the technology industry. Further, this finding contributes to some crucial human resources concerns in the

industry, such as work-life conflicts, absenteeism, and intensified work pressure (Conradie & Klerk, 2019). Therefore, organisations must provide options for remote work and more flexible hours to enable employees to effectively manage their professional and personal commitments. Moreover, implement flexible management initiatives to assist them effectively handle the ongoing demands of the work. This may involve techniques to control lengthy commutes, prevent the practice of carrying work home, and encourage a more improved balance between work and life (Hyder & Rani, 2024). However, effective communication is also vital to obtaining the full output from the FWAs (Shifrin & Michel, 2021).

There are some reservations about the adequacy and number of studies examining the implementation of FWAs in the technology industry and their impact, which is crucial for a study like this. The majority of previous studies were done with cross-sectional, archived information that was unable to separate between various types or applications of flexibility. So, future investigations ought to include more multi-wave and longitudinal evaluations of such correlations. Consequently, future research should incorporate more comprehensive and longitudinal analyses to investigate these relationships. Given the varied outcomes of different applications of FWAs, it is necessary to investigate many different types of flexibility (Shifrin & Michel, 2021).

Further, it is noted that most of the studies utilised in the present investigation have obtained data through online survey. In light of the nature of these online survey procedures, there may be some bias in the responses provided by the respondents. Thus, future research should take into consideration these factors and strive to eliminate bias (Conradie & Klerk, 2019). Furthermore, the studies incorporated to this systematic review mostly cover regions such as South Asia, West Africa, and the Middle East. To enhance comprehension of the impact of FWAs, future studies should thoroughly investigate certain contexts and demographic categories (Hyder & Rani, 2024).

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